

Empowering Non-Specialist Teachers and Students in Coding: A Case Study of a Python MOOC in an Austrian High School

Daniela Wolf¹ and Martin Ebner²

¹ Ferdinand Porsche FernFH, Ferdinand Porsche Ring 3, 2700 Wr. Neustadt, Austria
daniela.wolf@fernfh.ac.at

² Technische Universität Graz, Rechbauerstraße 12, 8010 Graz, Austria
martin.ebner@tugraz.at

Abstract. This paper explores the integration of a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) into the computer science curriculum of fifth-grade classes at an Austrian high school (so called „Gymnasium“) to introduce students to Python programming. A total of 42 students were surveyed, and two non-specialist teachers with no to little programming experience were interviewed to assess the MOOC's impact and practical feasibility. While the MOOC provided a valuable entry point for many students in programming and online learning, the results also highlighted several challenges. Although over half of the students (57%) rated the MOOC as ‘very useful’ or ‘useful’, motivation for further self-learning was moderate, and only a subset expressed interest in continuing coding independently. Teachers appreciated the structured content and expert-led videos, which enabled them to facilitate programming instruction despite their limited technical background. However, they also reported difficulties in meeting the diverse pacing needs of students. These findings indicate that while MOOCs can offer accessible resources for both students and non-specialist teachers, their effectiveness depends on thoughtful integration and scaffolding. The study offers insights into the conditions under which MOOCs may support secondary level coding education, particularly in contexts with limited access to qualified computer science educators.

Keywords: MOOCs, Non-specialist Teachers, Programming Instruction.

1 Introduction

In Austria, many high schools are experiencing a shortage of adequately trained computer science teachers, leading to non-specialist educators being assigned to teach the subject. As a result, computer science instruction is often limited to basic software applications like Microsoft Word, Excel, and PowerPoint, rather than introducing students to the fundamental principles of programming. Considering this, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) present a promising alternative that could not only provide students with up-to-date content and a self-paced learning environment, which is especially valuable in rapidly evolving fields like coding and technology but also enable

non-specialist teachers to effectively facilitate programming instruction. Therefore, this study explores the potential of MOOCs to enhance coding education in schools, specifically through the integration of a Python programming MOOC into a 5th-grade high school. The study focuses on examining students' perceptions of the MOOC overall, as well as its perceived contribution to the development of their programming competencies. The research also explores the challenges faced by non-specialist teachers, with limited formal training in computer science, and the potential benefits they see in using the MOOC as a tool to facilitate coding instruction. The central research question is: *How can MOOCs be implemented to enhance students' coding skills in secondary education, particularly when non-specialist teachers, with limited formal training in computer science, are responsible for teaching the subject?* By examining this, the study aims to shed light on how MOOCs can help non-specialist educators teach programming, offering a potential solution to the shortage of qualified computer science teachers in schools and improving access to quality coding education for secondary students.

2 Prior Work

While much of the research has focused on MOOCs in higher education, their application in secondary schools (age 10 to 18), particularly for teaching coding, remains underexplored [4, 8, 11]. In Finland, Kurhila and Vivahainen [10] reported that several high schools incorporated a MOOC corresponding to the University of Helsinki's Computer Science 1 course, offering formal credits in programming upon completion. In Austria, Khalil and Ebner [8] examined the "Mechanics in Everyday Life" MOOC for high school students using learning analytics. Although many participants perceived the course more as an additional homework assignment, the findings indicated that MOOCs have potential when they are meaningfully integrated into the classroom and accompanied by teacher guidance [8]. In Germany [2, 11, 14], as well as in countries such as the United States, Thailand, and Israel [3, 5, 12, 13], research has also examined the potential of MOOCs to support the development of technical skills, particularly programming and coding, among younger students. This highlights the increasing recognition of MOOCs as a valuable tool for developing essential skills in secondary education. In an era of rapid technological change, understanding how these systems function is increasingly critical for both academic success and future career development. Moreover, MOOCs provide students with the opportunity to familiarize themselves with digital tools and learning platforms, boosting their digital readiness and information literacy [4]. Additionally, MOOCs present a scalable solution for schools dealing with resource constraints or a shortage of specialized teaching staff as they are offering ready-made, pedagogically structured and excellent resource materials [7]. By providing up-to-date content, MOOCs can fill gaps that traditional curricula may lack [2]. However, there is little to no research on how MOOCs can specifically support non-specialist teachers in secondary education, where teacher shortages in subjects like computer science are common. Furthermore, a consistent challenge with MOOCs is that self-paced learning environments require strong self-regulation skills and motivation [9]. Secondary school students often struggle with the autonomy required by MOOCs. As a result, it has been suggested that MOOCs for this age

group should incorporate support mechanisms, such as blended learning, to maintain engagement and motivation [8]. Yet, empirical evidence on how online and face-to-face components should be integrated remains limited [15, 16]. One possible approach is to leverage well-developed and content-rich MOOCs while providing accompanying in-person sessions to offer structure and support to learners. Specifically, this could involve integrating live or archived MOOCs into an existing computer science course in a hybrid format [1], or adopting a flipped classroom model, where the MOOC enables students to review relevant material in advance, preparing them for in-class discussions [15]. This combination of online and face-to-face learning can create a balanced environment that meets the needs of diverse learners. In previous studies, students also reported a positive experience, highlighting that the face-to-face classes helped them stay on track with the self-paced MOOC component [1].

3 Method

This study used a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to evaluate the impact of the Python MOOC. Participants included 42 students (aged 14-15) and two non-specialist teachers. The students completed the MOOC as part of their mandatory computer science course in the summer semester of 2023 (3 classes, including one all-girls class), and in the winter semester of 2023/24 (2 classes), while the teachers facilitated the course with the help of solution guides and the support of a professionally qualified computer science teacher. The evaluation included post-MOOC surveys assessing students' engagement, motivation, and skills, along with interviews with the teachers about their experiences. The student questionnaire consisted of 24 questions: 18 closed-ended questions with a single response option, 4 multiple-choice questions, and 2 open-ended questions. For closed-ended questions, participants selected for example responses such as 'Very useful', 'Useful', 'Moderately useful', or 'Less useful' regarding the MOOC's impact on learning programming skills. Open-ended questions allowed for detailed reflections on improvements and challenges. The two teachers were interviewed orally without a structured interview guide, allowing for flexible and reflective conversations. Based on these interviews, a more structured teacher questionnaire was developed, consisting of 22 questions: 15 requiring a single answer, 4 with multiple responses, and 3 open-ended questions on improvements and challenges. Both teachers completed the questionnaire following the interview, and their responses were included in the analysis of the results.

4 MOOC Integration

The live Python programming MOOC, *Programmieren lernen mit Python - Schulversion*¹, offered through the HPI Open School and designed for beginners with no prior knowledge, was integrated into the classroom setting. Unlike many MOOCs that are primarily designed for adults or higher education contexts, this course is tailored to

¹ <https://open.hpi.de/courses/pythonjunior-schule2024>

meet the needs of school students to close the gap in computer science education in German schools [14]. The availability of the MOOC in German - a rarity within the predominantly English-speaking MOOC landscape - combined with its synchronous format and timely release at a pedagogically advantageous point in the school year, were additional factors that significantly influenced its selection. Moreover, the MOOC was chosen for its combination of video tutorials, interactive exercises, and continuous support from the providers, creating a well-balanced approach between self-directed learning and guided assistance. This didactic design not only promotes the understanding of programming concepts but also boosts student motivation and engagement, making it an ideal tool for both students and teachers in secondary education.

Furthermore, the installation of programming environments is often a significant challenge in computer science classroom. It can be time-consuming and technically demanding, especially for teachers without a computer science background. The MOOC addresses this issue by allowing students to program directly in the browser, eliminating the need for additional software installation [11, 14]. This feature simplifies the learning process and ensures that students and teachers can focus on coding rather than the technical setup. In addition, the tool automatically grades students' work by running tests to verify if their solutions meet the specified requirements, providing immediate feedback [14]. This automated grading system not only enhances the learning experience for students but also offers valuable support to teachers.

The implementation of the MOOC in the classroom was carried out in stages to ensure a smooth adaptation for both students and teachers. In the initial lesson, teachers provided an overview of the MOOC's objectives and guided students through the platform. After this introduction, the class collectively watched the first video, which introduced the first programming example, "Hello World." Following the video, students completed the first of three exercises in collaboration with the teacher, while the second and third exercise was intended for independent completion. Following this approach, each topic (such as variables, strings, data types, etc.) was progressively covered. This collaborative approach ensured that students developed a thorough understanding of the material before transitioning to more independent work. Each class started with a Kahoot quiz, created by the computer science teacher, to review the key points from the previous MOOC content, and to ensure that students had a solid grasp of the foundational concepts before progressing to new content. This structure facilitated a continuous cycle of learning, gradually increasing students' independence.

5 Results

A total of 42 students, including 28 females, participated in the questionnaire. Although engineering MOOCs report a low registration and participation rate of female students [6] the relatively high number of 27 women in our study can be attributed to the fact that we worked with one all-girls class and four mixed-gender classes, which likely contributed to the higher female participation in our study.

The interviews with the teachers (one male and one female) were also conducted after the implementation of the MOOC, in order to capture their experiences and insights regarding the integration of the course into the classroom.

5.1 Previous Knowledge of MOOCs (n=42)

The evaluation results revealed that a significant majority of students, 86% (36 students), had no prior experience with MOOCs, marking this as their first interaction with this type of learning format. Additionally, 12% (5 students) had heard of MOOCs but had not directly engaged with one, while only 2% (1 student) had occasionally used MOOCs before.

Table 1. Previous Experience with MOOCs (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
No, I didn't know what a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) was before the MOOC.	36	11	25	86%
No, I had heard of MOOCs but had no direct experience with them.	5	3	2	12%
Yes, I occasionally use MOOCs in my free time.	1	0	1	2%

5.2 Previous Programming Experience (n=42)

The data on previous programming experience showed that 64% (27 students) had no programming background. 24% (10 students) had some experience from previous school, while 12% (5 students) engaged in programming occasionally in their free time.

Table 2. Previous Experience with Programming (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Yes, I occasionally program in my free time.	5	3	2	12%
No, I had never programmed before the MOOC.	27	9	18	64%
Yes, I had programmed before the MOOC in class.	10	2	8	24%

5.3 Python Experience (n=15)

The results indicated that most students had minimal exposure to Python. Specifically, 47% (7 students) had no experience. This corresponds to 17% of the total 42 students. Additionally, 20% (3 students) had basic experience in Python. 20% (3 students) were

familiar with Python but lacked hands-on experience. Only 13% (2 students) possessed advanced Python skills. 27 participants did not provide an answer.

Table 3. Previous Experience with Python (n=15).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Yes, I have worked a lot with Python and can develop larger programs.	2	2	0	13%
Yes, I have written some small programs in Python.	3	0	3	20%
Yes, I have seen Python code but have never programmed myself.	3	2	1	20%
No, I have never worked with Python.	7	1	6	47%

5.4 Ease of Navigation in the MOOC (n=15)

The findings show that 53% (8 students) found the MOOC platform to be user-friendly and intuitive, allowing them to navigate it with ease. This corresponds to 19% of the total 42 students. Another 33% (5 students) needed a brief adjustment period but ultimately adapted to the platform without significant issues, which represents 12% of the total 42 students. Meanwhile, 14% (2 student) encountered challenges with navigation, finding some aspects of the course setup confusing. 27 participants did not provide an answer.

Table 4. Ease of Navigation on the MOOC Platform (n=15).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Yes, I quickly got used to the MOOC. The platform was user-friendly and intuitively designed, allowing me to navigate the course easily.	8	3	5	53%
Yes, I found my way around the MOOC relatively quickly. Although it took some time to get used to the interface, I was able to orient myself well after a short time.	5	2	3	33%
No, it took me a while to get used to the MOOC. The navigation and use of the platform were confusing at first, but I got better over time.	1	0	1	7%
No, at first, I had trouble navigating the MOOC. The platform was complex, and it took a while to familiarize myself with the features.	1	0	1	7%

5.5 Difficulty Level of the MOOC (n=15)

The difficulty level of the MOOC was generally considered appropriate by 33% (5 students) and well-balanced by 40% (6 students). 27% (4 students) found the

difficulty level of the MOOC too high. Out of the total of 42 students, 14% considered the MOOC well-balanced, 12% found it appropriate, 10% found it difficult, and 27 students did not provide an answer.

Table 5. Perceived Difficulty Level of the MOOC (n=15).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
The difficulty of the MOOC was well-balanced. The course presented challenges but was still achievable and motivated me to give my best.	6	3	3	40%
The difficulty of the MOOC was too high for me. The content was demanding and required a lot of background knowledge that I didn't always have.	4	0	4	27%
I found the difficulty level of the MOOC appropriate. The content was well-structured and built on itself, allowing me to continuously expand my knowledge.	5	2	3	33%

5.6 Enjoyment of the MOOC (n=15)

60% (9 students) liked the MOOC overall, while 40% (6 students) did not find it as appealing. Out of the total of 42 students, 21% liked the MOOC, 14% did not find it as appealing, and 27 students provided no answer.

Table 6. Overall Enjoyment of the MOOC (n=15).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
The MOOC did not appeal to me particularly.	6	2	4	40%
I really liked the MOOC.	1	1	0	7%
I mostly liked the MOOC.	8	2	6	53%

The results of the questionnaire revealed that the most enjoyed aspects of the MOOC were the ability to control the learning pace and the improvement in programming skills, with ten students mentioning both. Eight students appreciated the flexibility to choose their learning location. Additionally, five students found the ability to effectively apply what they learned to be particularly valuable. Two students highlighted the positive impact the MOOC had on their learning curve, due to its well-structured content and clear learning objectives.

5.7 Strengths and Challenges (n=15)

The most frequently mentioned advantage, cited by eleven participants, was the ability to learn at their own pace. Six participants highlighted the flexibility of the course, particularly the ability to adapt learning time and location. Two students appreciated

the self-directed learning aspect, while one participant noted the benefits of collaborative learning and increased interactivity. The most frequent issue was *"less interaction with other students in the classroom"*, mentioned by three participants. Other concerns included *"motivation difficulties"*, *"lack of individual customization"*, and *"lack of direct feedback"* each noted by two participants. The challenges they encountered while using the MOOC included technical issues such as server overload and problems with account details, like username deletion. Some students found it difficult to follow the videos and retain all the information, while others noted that the system only accepted one solution path, even when their answers were correct. There were also cases where the system incorrectly marked answers as wrong despite them being correct.

Students felt that the videos were either too boring or lacked excitement, and they suggested making the videos more interesting and engaging. Specific suggestions included adding more dynamic elements to the videos, improving their clarity, and providing better explanations for the steps involved. A few participants also mentioned the need for more variety in the solutions presented in the exercises, as well as clearer instructions and additional support when encountering difficulties. Some also requested better feedback from the instructors and the ability to ask questions directly to the teachers, rather than relying on peers.

5.8 Perceived Usefulness of the MOOC for Learning Programming Skills (n=42)

The evaluation results for the perceived usefulness of the MOOC in learning programming skills reveal that 14% (6 students) considered it very useful, while 43% (18 students) found it useful. Additionally, 38% (16 students) rated its usefulness as average, with 5% (2 students) finding it less useful.

Table 7. Perceived Usefulness of the MOOC for Learning Programming Skills (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Very useful: The MOOC was extremely useful for learning programming skills.	6	5	1	14%
Useful: The MOOC was useful for learning programming skills.	18	5	13	43%
Average useful: The MOOC was moderately useful for learning programming skills.	16	4	12	38%
Less useful: The MOOC was less useful for learning programming skills.	2	0	2	5%

5.9 Recommendation of the MOOC to Other Students (n=42)

The survey results on whether students would recommend the MOOC to others show a range of opinions. About 16% (7 students) indicated they would for sure recommend, while 24% (10 students) would likely recommend it. 50% (21 students)

responded with "maybe". Meanwhile, 10% (4 students) were not likely to recommend the course.

Table 8. Likelihood of Recommending the MOOC to Others (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Yes, definitely	7	4	3	16%
Yes, probably	10	4	6	24%
Maybe	21	6	15	50%
No, rather not	4	0	4	10%

5.10 Interest in Using MOOCs in Other Subjects (n=42)

The survey results on students' interest in using MOOCs for other subjects reveal moderate enthusiasm. About 64% (27 students) indicated they might consider using MOOCs in other subjects. About 19% (8 students) indicated they might not consider. 12% (5 students) saw potential benefits in integrating MOOCs into different areas of study, and 5% (2 students) were interested in this expansion.

Table 9. Students' Interest in Using MOOCs for Other Subjects (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Yes, definitely	2	2	0	5%
Yes, probably	5	3	2	12%
Maybe	27	8	19	64%
No, rather not	8	1	7	19%

5.11 Motivation for Continued Self-Learning (n=42)

The evaluation results regarding motivation indicate that 48% (20 students) felt a moderate level of motivation from participating in the MOOC. Meanwhile, 26% (11 students) reported feeling less motivated, and 26% (11 students) felt encouraged by the MOOC to pursue further self-directed learning.

Table 10. Motivation Levels from Participation in the MOOC (n=42).

Response	Total	Male	Female	Percentage
Motivated	11	7	4	26%
Less motivated	11	4	7	26%
Average motivated	20	3	17	48%

5.12 Teacher Feedback (n=2)

Both teachers had basic programming knowledge, mostly gained through Scratch or as part of professional development courses. One teacher had some little experience with Python, while the other had never worked with it before.

Neither of the teachers had previous experience using MOOCs, either as participants or in classroom settings. While they were familiar with the term "MOOC" and had heard of MOOCs, they had no direct experience with them. Despite this lack of experience, both teachers found their way around the MOOC quickly. The platform was user-friendly and intuitively designed, allowing them to navigate the course without any difficulties. They also observed that the students adapted to the platform just as quickly. The teachers rated the quality of the videos and other learning resources highly, noting that they were well-suited to engage students and facilitate understanding. They did not encounter any technical issues, suggesting that the MOOC platform was stable and accessible. The teachers also noted that it was extremely helpful to receive the solutions to exercises in advance from the professionally qualified computer science teacher. For students who progressed quickly through the MOOC, they distributed the example solutions and encouraged the students to independently identify errors. This approach proved valuable, especially for the non-specialist computer science teachers, who often face difficulties in providing further support when students move beyond the material. By giving students the solutions, they could work through the problems themselves and find solutions independently, which also fostered problem-solving skills and deeper engagement with the content. The teachers considered the MOOC *"very useful"* for teaching programming skills, appreciating its structured and clear content, which supported student comprehension. They expressed in general, that the quotes *"The MOOC was somewhat monotonous, but it was fun and something different. We really learned programming. It was meaningful"* were frequently mentioned from the students in the classroom. The teachers also expressed confidence in recommending the MOOC to other educators, especially those who may need additional structure and support to teach programming. The experience also inspired the teachers to consider using MOOCs for their own professional development, recognizing the platform's potential as a valuable learning tool for both students and teachers. Given the limited number of teachers involved in this research study, it is not intended to inform future decisions or provide a comprehensive overview. Instead, we aim to present a new study that also explores the use of MOOCs by non-specialist teachers.

6 Discussion

The results from this study highlight both the strengths and challenges of integrating a Python programming MOOC into secondary education. The majority of students (86%) had no prior experience with MOOCs, making this their first exposure to such a learning format. This is significant because it underscores the MOOC's potential in reaching students who are new to MOOC learning environments. Additionally, the students' previous programming experience was largely limited, with 64% having no background in coding, suggesting that the MOOC served as an introductory tool for many. In terms of navigation, most students found the MOOC platform to be user-friendly, with 53% reporting a seamless experience. This aligns with findings from Staubitz et al. [14], where a positive user experience with the MOOC platform was observed despite initial challenges. However, some students expressed difficulties, with 14% struggling with navigation. This disparity between ease of use and

difficulties could reflect differences in digital readiness among students, as MOOCs often demand a higher level of autonomy compared to traditional learning formats. As the study by Grella et al. [2], has shown, a lack of teacher guidance in the absence of in-person interactions can lead to frustration among students, affecting their engagement and satisfaction with the platform. When asked about the difficulty level of the course, 26% of the total 42 students considered the MOOC to be appropriate and well-balanced, while 10% found it too challenging. This suggests that while the MOOC was generally effective for a wide range of learners, some students might need additional scaffolding or support to succeed. These findings resonate with Grover et al. [3], where the combination of traditional teaching and MOOC content in a Blended Learning environment was found to be beneficial in improving understanding, particularly for students with less prior knowledge. The integration of face-to-face interactions may have helped address challenges related to the difficulty and engagement of the content. The enjoyment of the course was relatively high for $n=15$, with 60% of students expressing enjoyment. However, when considering the total of 42 students, only 21% rated the MOOC as overall enjoyable, while 64% (27 students) did not provide an answer. The higher levels of enjoyment reported by a subset of students align with other studies, such as Panyajamorn et al. [12], which highlighted the positive impact of MOOCs on student engagement, particularly when students felt motivated and were able to progress at their own pace. However, the 50% lower satisfaction among all students in this study suggests that personalization and engagement need further improvement. Specifically, students cited a lack of interaction with other students and the teacher, which echoes findings from Grella et al. [2], where the limited interaction with instructors and peers was considered a major challenge. This calls for MOOCs to incorporate more interactive elements and community-building opportunities for the class itself. Students also reported technical difficulties, such as server overload and errors marking correct answers as incorrect. These challenges mirror the findings of Hermans & Aivaloglou [5], where technical issues and system reliability were identified as key barriers to students' learning experiences in MOOC environments. Improving system stability and interactive video formats could address some of these concerns, as suggested by students who asked for clearer explanations and more engaging videos. Interestingly, the study also showed moderate interest in extending the use of MOOCs to other subjects, though it was not overwhelming. This suggests that broader adoption across different subjects in secondary schools may require further investigation into content suitability and student interest. This reflects the need for content adaptation identified in Staubitz et al. [14], where content for MOOCs needs to be tailored more specifically to both the subject matter and student needs to maximize effectiveness.

The feedback from the teachers was also insightful. Despite having limited experience with MOOCs, both teachers found the course to be user-friendly and appreciated the clarity of the videos and learning resources. This feedback aligns with the findings of Sharkia and Kohen [13], which indicate that MOOCs, particularly when taught by university-level experts and integrated into hybrid learning environments, might serve as a particularly valuable tool for non-specialist teachers. By providing access to expert instruction and well-structured content, MOOCs can complement or extend teachers' own subject knowledge, thereby enhancing their ability to support student

learning. In your study, the teachers emphasized that the MOOC allowed them to guide students more effectively. However, they also mentioned the challenge of providing adequate support for students progressing faster than others. This reflects the importance of providing additional resources, such as solutions and teaching guides, which was also observed in other studies like Grella et al. [2]. Teachers found the MOOC to be a valuable tool for teaching programming and expressed confidence in recommending it to other educators, further supporting the idea that MOOCs, when well-integrated, can bridge the gap in teaching resources, especially in subjects facing teacher shortages.

7 Conclusion and Future Steps

This study presents initial findings, though not representative, suggesting that MOOCs, particularly in subjects such as computer science, hold significant potential by offering flexibility, structured, engaging instruction; help to bridge the CS teacher gap; enable scalable, accessible integration of programming in schools, and support long-term improvement of digital education in secondary schools. However, challenges such as technical difficulties, motivation issues, and the need for more interactive and personalized support highlight areas for improvement. These findings underscore the importance of designing MOOCs that ensure sustained engagement, particularly in self-paced learning environments. As MOOCs continue to gain traction in secondary education, further research and development are needed to refine their design and optimize their impact.

Limitation

This study has several limitations: the small overall sample size - particularly among teachers - limits the generalizability of the findings; the absence of additional indicators such as student learning outcomes restricts the evaluation of the MOOC's overall effectiveness; and the optional nature of questionnaire items led to varying response rates (e.g., $n = 15$ vs. $n = 42$), affecting the comparability of specific results.

References

1. Bruff, D. O., Fisher, D. H., McEwen, K. E. & Smith, B. E. (2013). Wrapping a MOOC: Student perceptions of an experiment in blended learning. *MERLOT Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 9(2), 187–199. Retrieved from http://jolt.merlot.org/vol9no2/bruff_0613.htm
2. Grella, C. T., Staubitz, T., Teusner, R. & Meinel, C. (2017). *Can MOOCs Support Secondary Education in Computer Science?* Hasso Plattner Institute for IT-Systems Engineering, University of Potsdam.
3. Grover, S., Pea, R. & Cooper, S. (2015). Designing for deeper learning in a blended computer science course for middle school students. *Computer Science Education*, 25(2), 199–237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08993408.2015.1033142>

4. Guggemos, J., Moser, L. & Seufert, S. (2022). Learners don't know best: Shedding light on the phenomenon of the K-12 MOOC in the context of information literacy. *Computers & Education*, 188, 104552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104552>
5. Hermans, F. & Aivaloglou, E. (2017). Teaching Software Engineering Principles to K-12 Students: A MOOC on Scratch. In *Proceedings of the 2017 IEEE/ACM 39th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering Education and Training Track (ICSE-SEET)* (S. 13–22). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-SEET.2017.13>
6. Ihsen, S., Jeanrenaud, Y. & de Vries, P. (2015). Gender and Diversity in Engineering MOOCs: A First Appraisal. In *Proceedings of the 43rd Annual SEFI Conference* (S. 1–10). SEFI.
7. Israel, M. J. (2015). Effectiveness of Integrating MOOCs in Traditional Classrooms for Undergraduate Students. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(5), 102–119.
8. Khalil, M. & Ebner, M. (2015). A STEM MOOC for school children: What does learning analytics tell us? In *2015 International Conference on Interactive Collaborative Learning (ICL)* (S. 1217–1221). IEEE.
9. Kizilcec, R. F. & Schneider, E. (2015). Motivation as a Lens to Understand Online Learners: Toward Data-Driven Design with the OLEI Scale. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 22(2), 6–23.
10. Kurhila, J. & Vihavainen, A. (2015). A purposeful MOOC to alleviate insufficient CS education in Finnish schools. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, 15(2), 10:1–10:18.
11. Löwis, M., Staubitz, T., Teusner, R., Renz, J. & Meinel, C. (2015). Scaling Youth Development Training in IT Using an xMOOC-Platform. In *2015 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)* (S. 1–6). IEEE.
12. Panyajamorn, T., Kohda, Y., Chongphaisal, P. & Supnithi, T. (2016). The effectiveness and suitability of MOOCs hybrid learning: A case study of public schools in Thai rural area. In *11th International Conference on Knowledge, Information and Creativity Support Systems (KICSS)* (S. 1–6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/KICSS.2016.7951449>
13. Sharkia, H. & Kohen, Z. (2025). “Simply Math”—A Hybrid MOOC Supporting Advanced Mathematics Learning in Israeli Secondary Schools. *Education Sciences*, 15(3), 271. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15030271>
14. Staubitz, T., Teusner, R. & Meinel, C. (2019). MOOCs in Secondary Education – Experiments and Observations from German Classrooms. In *2019 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)* (S. 173–182). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON.2019.8725193>
15. Thai, T. T. N., De Wever, B. & Valcke, M. (2017). The impact of a flipped classroom design on learning performance in higher education: Looking for the best “blend” of lectures and guiding questions with feedback. *Computers & Education*, 107, 113–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.01.003>
16. Vo, H. M., Zhu, C. & Diep, N. A. (2017). The effect of blended learning on student performance at course-level in higher education: A meta-analysis. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 53, 17–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2017.01.002>